

1 **ZXDA and ZXDB, nuclear factors associated with Xist imprinting, might have functions in**
2 **switching at developmental stage transitions across lineage types.**

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7 Citations

8 1. Al-Kandari, W., Koeni, R., Naval Gund, V., Aleksandrova, A., Jambunathan, S. and Fontes, J.D.,
9 2007. The zinc finger proteins ZXDA and ZXDC form a complex that binds CIITA and regulates MHC II
10 gene transcription. *Journal of molecular biology*, 369(5), pp.1175-1187.

11 2. Tomkins, D.J., McDonald, H.L., Farrell, S.A. and Brown, C.J., 2002. Lack of expression of XIST
12 from a small ring X chromosome containing the XIST locus in a girl with short stature, facial dysmorphism
13 and developmental delay. *European Journal of Human Genetics*, 10(1), pp.44-51.

14 3. Dibus, N., Korinek, V. and Cermak, L., 2022. FBXO38 ubiquitin ligase controls centromere
15 integrity via ZXDA/B stability. *Frontiers in Cell and Developmental Biology*, 10, p.929288.